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Narrative Techniques and Youth-Centric Storytelling in Chetan Bhagat's Novels

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Abstract:

Creative writers use umpteen narrative techniques and narrative devices to capture the attention of the reader, to convey what they want, and also to give certain artistic and emotional effects to a story. They provide deeper meaning for the reader and help them imagine or visualise situations. Key narrative techniques fall into five categories namely setting, plot, character, point of view, and style.

In the present paper, a study is made on the storytelling techniques and other stylistic devices employed by Chetan Bhagat in his early novels *Five Point Someone*, *One Night @ the Call Center* and a later novel *One Indian Girl*. In the recent past, Chetan Bhagat became the biggest celebrity in the Indian literary landscape evoking the most intense reactions. Readers love him for telling stories to which they feel they can relate. His stories and style of narration reflect the life of a modern-day youth in a big way, and that is why youngsters are crazy about his writings because the readers see themselves being reflected in the novels. His writing style tends to be simple, with linear narratives, and vivid storytelling. His columns and articles are written in simple English and discussed in the Indian Parliament. Most of his novels follow first-person narration. The tone of his novels is always maintained as that of a jolly good college boy who does not care about the travails of the day-to-day.

Keywords: Narrative techniques, narrative devices, storytelling, flashback, first-person point of view.

Creative writers employ umpteen narrative techniques – setting, plot, character, point of view, and style – and narrative devices – flashback, first-person narration, *deus ex machina*, internal monologue, prologue/epilogue, and conversational tone – to capture the attention of the reader, to convey their ideas, and also to give certain artistic and emotional effects to their stories. They often use their own voice or create characters and narrator agents to express their concerns and responses. They endeavour to understand and unravel the complex facets of human nature and showcase their attitudes and behaviours through various narrative techniques. Such narrative techniques become the most important aspects of imaginative literature, as the nature of the narrative and the mode of narration guide the reader to the meaning of a work of art. They provide more profound meaning for the reader and help them imagine or visualise situations. Key narrative techniques, which shape a narrative and its meaning, fall into five categories namely setting, plot, character, point of view, and style. These elements relay “information to the audience and, particularly, to ‘develop’ the narrative, usually in order to make it more complete, complicated, or interesting” (A.R. Rahman).

Chetan Bhagat, a columnist, screenwriter, and YouTuber, is the most recent and widely read post-modern Indian author whose novels “have been best-selling hits despite much criticism” (Monika Monalisa, 2024). He has won acclaim by writing novels using different narrative techniques. He believes that authentic creativity comes from within and by reading the works of renowned writers. He likes to read the works of Earnest Hemingway, George Orwell, and R.K. Narayan whom he considers icons in his life. Influenced by these writers, Bhagat often explores themes of youth, love, and social issues in his novels including class disparity, corruption, the pressure of academic success, and the struggles of young

professionals in India. They provoke the young Indian graduates to read thereby developing a reading habit which is almost a forgotten skill among the current generation. In an interview given to Forbes India magazine, he says, “I’ve always written young people, as that is the age one gets influenced most by books. ... I’d say I still write for somewhat younger Indians, who are of course educated” (Chetan Bhagat, 2009). His writing style is simple and tends the young reader to complete the reading of the novel with ease. He uses an informal, conversational tone that mirrors how young people speak in India.

Chetan Bhagat is the author of ten novels entitled *Five Point Someone* (2004), *One Night @ the Call Center* (2005), *The 3 Mistakes of My Life* (2008), *2 States* (2009), *Revolution 2020* (2011), *Half Girlfriend* (2014), *One Indian Girl* (2016), *The Girl in Room 105* (2018), *One Arranged Murder* (2020), and *400 Days* (2021). Besides these, he has written four non-fictional works namely *What Young India Wants* (2012), *Making India Awesome* (2015), *India Positive* (2019), and *11 Rules for Life: Secrets to Level Up* (2024). All these works focus on youth and urban India, making him very popular among urban audience and garnering a strong following among Indian youth. Bhagat employs an innovative mode of narration that easily draws the readers’ attention. Due to his contribution to the literary world, *Time* magazine listed him as the “World’s 100 Most Influential People in 2010.” His name is even listed among the “100 Most Creative People 2011” by the *Fast Company*, an American Business Magazine, and “*Forbes India* Celebrity 100 List” in 2017. He has received several awards such as the Society Young Achiever’s Award (2000), and Golden Book Award (2022).

Despite his success and contribution, some distinguished academic writers, literati, and literary critics dismiss Bhagat’s novels arguing that they lack depth and complexity. They dismiss his novels as they often rely on clichés and formulaic plots. They even believe that his novels are less sophisticated compared to other Indian authors. Besides this, they also content that his novels appropriate register, deep symbolism, and above all profound themes typically

associated with literary fiction. In a nutshell, they say that his novels are commercially successful and influential in popularizing English fiction in India, but his writing lacks the artistic complexity and nuance that are hallmarks of literary fiction. His works are primarily regarded as entertaining, accessible, and socially relevant, rather than being categorized as literary masterpieces. Reacting to such remarks, Chetan Bhagat, at the 2024 India Today Mind Rocks Youth Summit, said that “one should not be swayed by external feedback, whether positive or negative” (Manisha Pandey, 2024).

The objective of this paper is to analyse the narrative techniques employed by Chetan Bhagat in his early novels namely *Five Point Someone*, *One Night @ the Call Center* and a later novel *One Indian Girl*. These novels feature unique narrative styles and follow a formulaic structure, typically showcasing young protagonists, urban settings, and conflicts that are resolved in emotionally satisfying, yet predictable ways. Through the use of flashback technique, the author realistically narrates the incidents which happened in the characters' real life. He has used a first-person narrative, which allows readers to connect intimately with the protagonist's experiences and emotions. For instance, in *Five Point Someone*, protagonist Hari narrates the story, offering his perspective on the struggles of academic life at an elite institution in an institution.

In literary works, the setting is one of the most important elements that affects a story. It is the context which includes the time, the place, the social environment, and the mood of the events of the story. It basically helps in establishing where, when, and under what circumstances the story is taking place. It may establish the atmosphere, or mood, of a story or a specific scene. Setting the appropriate mood also helps the audience relate themselves to the characters in a story. It may even assist the reader to relate to the incident, to the backdrop, and to the characters within a story. It can have immense effects on the plot and the characters, as

it could act as an antagonist, post a conflict that characters need to resolve, or could shed light upon characters, and could also present symbolic persons, objects, places, actions or situations.

In the novels of Chetan Bhagat, the setting effectively complements the mood, context, and story. The setting of *Five Point Someone* (2004) is the campus of the Indian Institute of Technology (IIT), Delhi, where much of the novel's action takes place. It begins with a mysterious prologue in which Hari, the narrator, and Ryan are in an ambulance with Alok. Hari narrates the story of himself and of his two friends, Alok and Ryan, who studied along with him at the IIT Campus in Delhi.

The scene of action in *One Night @ the Call Center* (2005) is set in an office where bored young employees like Shyam, Priyanka, Vroom, and others work. It is a call center that tries to resolve the mindless inquiries of Midwestern American Technophobes. Its story unfolds over the course of one night, during which the main characters confront aspects of themselves or their lives they wish to change. Similar to his first novel, Bhagat projects his own image of an eccentric and a crazy man in the minds of the readers. *The 3 Mistakes of My Life* (2008) begins in Ahmedabad where three friends – Gopi, Ishan, and Omi – live and dream of achieving something significant in their lives. In another powerful novel *2 States* the scene of action shifts from Indian Institute of Management (IIM), Ahmedabad to Chennai which is more relevant to the context and the situation. Bhagat's novel *Revolution 2020* (2011) is set in Varanasi on the banks of the Ganga River, while his reputed novel *Half Girlfriend* (2014) opens in New Delhi, the capital city of India.

Plot is the most vital element in any work of art. It refers to how incidents are arranged to make a story comprehensible to the reader. Writers employ different modes while narrating the story. Chetan Bhagat commonly uses the flashback technique in almost all of his novels. He typically opens them with a prologue creating a situation that allows him to present himself to the readers. Just as in our epics *Ramayana* and *Mahabharata* where the main story is narrated

through a character, Bhagat too introduces himself at the beginning of his novels in a scene which has connection to the main story.

Chetan Bhagat's *Five Point Someone* is written in the first-person perspective. He narrates the story through the eyes of the protagonist. The novel begins with the words of Hari Kumar, the protagonist thus:

Well, I have to start somewhere and what better than the day I joined the Indian Institute of Technology and met Ryan and Alok for the first time; we had adjacent rooms on the second floor of the Kumaon hostel. (*FPS* 01)

He is taking his friend Alok, who tried to commit suicide, to hospital in an ambulance. It is then the story shifts from the present to the past. He starts narrating the story of Alok Gupta, Ryan Oberoi, and himself. It is through his narration, the readers know the time they have spent in IIT Campus, Delhi. They hail from three different family backgrounds. Alok's mother is a school teacher and his father has been a patient for a long time. Half of his mother's salary goes towards his father's medical treatment. He has a marriageable sister too. So, he feels a deep sense of responsibility towards his family, strives to perform well in his studies so that he can get good grades and earn a job in a well-reputed concern.

Ryan's father and mother are intimately involved in business. They rarely visit India to see their son who was kept in a boarding school since his childhood. This upbringing fosters feelings of hatred and resentment towards his parents. It is evident in Ryan's words when he says, "I said I don't love my parents.... I don't know why. I mean, I have been in boarding school when I was six. Of course, like every kid I hated it and cried when they left me" (38-39). His boarding school gives him studies and entertainment. On the other side, Hari's case too is the same as Ryan. His father is a strict disciplinarian Colonel in the army. He joins IIT due to his father's compulsion, feeling neither love nor hatred for his parents.

In spite of different backgrounds, Alok and Ryan become good friends, share their sorrows, joys, and troubles. They remain underperformers academically and their grade point average never goes beyond six. But they create the C2D (Cooperate to Dominate) formula to save time and to share assignments. Though they come out with innovative ideas, the IIT never recognizes their creativity as it expects only grades. So, with a view to getting good grades in the final exam, they attempt to steal the question paper but are caught and suspended for six months. Alok thinks that they will not be allowed to write the exam and attempts suicide (the scene with which the novel begins). Fortunately, with the kind-heartedness of one of the Professors in campus, they write the final exam and ultimately secure placements in different companies.

One Night @ the Call Center is another best-selling novel that adopts a unique narrative technique. Chetan Bhagat infuses a dramatic and decisive twist to the story by employing the literary device known as *deus ex machina* (God from the machine). A phone call from God is an additional element in this novel. It begins with a frame story recounting a train journey from Kanpur to Delhi, during which the narrator-author meets a beautiful girl. She offers to tell the author a story on the condition that “you have to promise me to write it as your second book” (7). After much hesitation, the author agrees to listen to the story about “six people, three guys and three girls who worked at the Connexions Call Center” (9).

The main plot begins with the appearance of Shyam, Priyanka, Vroom, Esha, Radhika, and a Military uncle who work in the Connexions call center in Gurgaon, Haryana. All of them live in their world of dreams. Shyam narrates the story of himself and the stories of all other characters. Through his narration, the readers learn that they suffer from various problems such as lost love, thwarted ambitions, absence of family affection, pressures of a patriarchal set-up, and the challenges of a globalized work environment in the office.

Shyam is a daydreamer, often reminiscing about his past ex-girlfriend who rejected him due to her mother's disapproval. Priyanka, on the other hand, dreams of her intended husband, Ganesh, who earns a lot in America. One night, while returning from a break, they face a life-threatening situation when their Qualis car crashes into a construction site filled with precarious iron construction rods. As the rods began to yield slowly, they start to panic and soon realize that they cannot call for help due to a lack of mobile network coverage. Suddenly Shyam received a phone call from God which makes them think about their lives and also to change the lives of all people in the call center. The conversation with God motivates the group to confront their problems with utmost determination and motivation. Meanwhile, Vroom and Shyam hatch a plan to oust their boss, Bakshi, from the call center and prevent the closing of Connexions Call Center, whose employees are to be downsized radically. When they emerge from danger, they come out with clear-cut goals in their mind. On returning to the call center, they execute their plans with dexterity.

One Indian Girl (2016) deals with themes such as feminism, societal expectations, and the personal quest for happiness and fulfilment. It is perhaps the first novel that narrates the story of a girl in a female voice in the first-person point of view. Radhika Mehta, the central character, is intelligent yet grapples with the challenge of balancing her professional and personal life amidst various struggles. She is a twenty-seven-year-old woman and works as the Vice President of Goldman Sachs, an investment banking firm in New York. She is educated and wishes to live an independent life despite knowing the fact that society never accepts such an idea. Naturally, she faces challenges which stem from her success, personal insecurities, and patriarchal judgements. Her journey unfolds in flashbacks, where her relationships with her former lovers, Debashish Sen and Neel Gupta, are explored, and ultimately, her realization of self-worth leads her to make independent decisions, refusing to conform to societal pressures, including those imposed by her family.

The narration shifts to the present, where Radhika is preparing for her destination wedding in Goa with Brijesh Gulatia, a Software Engineering at Facebook in San Francisco. She is marrying Brijesh because she believes that he is very empathetic and caring towards her, and understands the equal opportunities and rights expected of her. She recollects past romantic involvements with Debu, her ex-boyfriend. She says that “I remember meeting Debu for the first time in New York. He was different then” (Bhagat 74). However, he changed his attitude and left her when he felt emasculated by her financial success. After their breakup, Radhika goes into a relationship with Neel, a married man who treats their relationship as casual, further complicating her life. Both these relationships affect her deeply, leaving her questioning her self-worth, both as a woman and as a successful professional.

As Radhika prepares for her wedding to Brijesh, a man she hardly knows but who seems like a safe choice, both Debu and Neel unexpectedly show up, each trying to win her back. This revelation prompts Radhika to confront her insecurities, past traumas, and the weight of societal expectations on her as a career-driven woman. Ultimately, she makes a bold decision to reject both men and chooses to embark on a world tour to discover her true self. She refuses to compromise her identity for the sake of fitting into traditional gender roles, thus delivering a strong feminist message.

In the novel, internal monologue plays a central role in the narrative, providing insight into Radhika’s struggle with societal expectations and her personal desires. Her constant internal questioning allows readers to see the dichotomy between what Radhika wants and what society expects of her. The author poignantly states that, “Why is it that a successful woman has to prove she’s more feminine, more likeable, just to be accepted?” (Bhagat 79). This line reflects the societal expectations and pressures faced by women, particularly those who are successful, who often feel the need to demonstrate certain qualities, like femininity and likability, to gain acceptance, despite their professional accomplishments. Bhagat uses

Radhika's character to voice these struggles while focusing on themes of feminism and gender roles.

Bhagat adopts a conversational style, throughout the novel, making it relatable to modern readers. The tone is casual and reflective of contemporary urban Indian English, enhancing the text's accessibility. For instance, "I mean, seriously? Does it even matter if I make more money than the guy?" (Bhagat 92). Deepak Dongre observes thus:

Chetan Bhagat is an intelligent writer to make use of the current themes and finds success in projecting these narratives in his novel. His recent attempt *One Indian Girl* is a well-trying effort to bring the inner voices of an ambitious girl.

Bhagat's characters are typically young and convey the message that a bad thing is to be turned down and a good thing is to be accepted whether it comes from an intellectual or from a layman. They fight for their aspirations and attempt to guide the youth in the proper direction. They believe in the dictum that success comes to those who crave for practicability but not for mugginess in life.

Bhagat's female characters emerge as 'new women' emphasizing personal liberty in their lives. They never hesitate to express their feelings but believe in an absolute, perfect, pure and genuine form of freedom. They are all modern with practicality and intellect. They won't represent the stereotypes or alter egos offering simplistic representation of women.

Bhagat's protagonists often resemble avatars of Hindu deities, such as Hari, Shyam, Govind or Krishna. He writes for 'ordinary young people' who feel suffocated by their parents' desire for them to become doctors, lawyers, or engineers and so on. He generally talks about youngsters' worries, their anxieties and all those things which preoccupy them, using his writings. His writing subjects include parental academic pressure along with pre-marital sex, drinking and other topics that are always considered taboo in socially conservative India.

The secret to Chetan Bhagat's success lies in his use of the first-person point of view. The readers, while reading his novels, may easily associate themselves with the characters and at times they get the feeling that they are reading the story of themselves. He, from his first novel to the latest novel, has used 'I' as the narrator which encourages readers to compare their experiences with that of the narrator. For example, his novel *Five Point Someone* begins with "I had never been inside an ambulance before." Even his novel entitled *Half Girlfriend* begins with Madhav narrating, "Where? I gasped, trying to catch my breath. I had two minutes left for my interview to start and I couldn't find the room" (1). Sometimes, he even breaks traditional novel formats and comes out innovatively by writing prologues and epilogues, and dividing the novels into Acts. All his books have a number in the title, for instance, 'five' in the first, 'one' in the second, 'three' in the third and 'two' in the fourth. When asked about this, Bhagat humorously remarked that he is a banker and he can't get numbers out of his head.

Chetan Bhagat writes in ordinary English allowing readers to complete the novel in one or two sittings without feeling any monotony. He uses the common man's idiom that makes the reader close to their heart. The language also tends to be simple with linear narratives and vivid storytelling. The tone is always maintained as that of a cheerful college student who does not care about the travails of day-to-day. For instance, the use of humour and light-hearted tones, as seen in the protagonist Hari's casual narration in *Five Point Someone*, serves as a coping mechanism for the youth facing societal pressures, offering a psychological respite rather than a profound critique.

To conclude, one may easily say that Chetan Bhagat, with different narrative styles, occupied a space for himself in the history of post-modern Indian writing in English. Readers love to read his books, compare the characters to themselves, relate their situations to that of the characters, and feel themselves being reflected in his novels. His stories and narrative style vividly reflect the life of a modern-day youth in a big way, and that is one reason why

youngsters are crazy about his writings. His novels have inspired reading initiatives in schools, where teachers use them to engage reluctant readers, blending entertainment with subtle life lessons on ambition and resilience. Commenting on the writings of Chetan Bhagat, Sunil Gomaji Chaudhari aptly remarks:

Every writer has his own style of narrating events and situations. Some allow in flights of fancy ... some furnish facts ... some refer to the ancient legends to show similarity or offer contrast in their claims. It is to the credit of Chetan Bhagat that he employs all these devices to make his description not only life-like but also living.

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